

**To What Extent Does Foreign Aid in South Sudan
Consider Conflict-Sensitive Approaches to
Development Intervention?**

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Content

Chapter 1: Introduction	8
The Rationale of the Study	8
Methodology	10
Conflict-Sensitivity: “Do No Harm”	12
Understanding the Environment	13
Chapter 2: Introduction: The South Sudan Crisis	19
South Sudan	19
The Conflict in South Sudan	22
Conflict Factors	24
The Intensity of the South Sudan Crisis	26
Chapter 3: Introduction: Foreign Aid Actors in South Sudan	31
Foreign Aid Actors and Participation in South Sudan’s Conflict and Post-Conflict Era	32
Country-Led Aid and Development Participation	33
The United States of America	33
The United Kingdom	36
Norway	38
Japan	41

Organization-Led Aid and Development Participation	44
United Nations	44
United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund	47
International Rescue Committee	51
United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees	52
World Bank	55
African Development Bank	58
Chapter 4: Introduction: Aid and Development Intervention Themes	62
Women's Peace and Security	62
Water, Sanitation and Hygiene	65
Food Security and Hunger Eradication	66
Quality Education	68
Health Care and Well-Being	69
Chapter 5: Introduction- Challenges and Observations	71
Challenges of Foreign Aid and Development Interventions in South Sudan	71
Learnings and Observations	72
References	74
Appendices	87

Acronyms

AfDB	African Development Bank
CERF	Central Emergency Response Fund
CSP	Country Strategic Plan
DCRNPI	Directorate for Civil Registry, Nationality, Passport, and Immigration
DFID	Department for International Development
ECHO	European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations
EFPP	Emergency Food Production Programme
EIF	Enhanced Integrated Framework
ERLP	Emergency Locust Response Project
ERW	Explosives Remnants of War
FCDO	Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office
FOA	Food and Agriculture Organization
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GoSS	Government of South Sudan
GoRSS	Government of the Republic of South Sudan
GPE	Global Partnership for Education
GPS	Gender, Peace, and Security
IAR	Impact Area Report

I-CSP	Interim Country Strategy Paper
IDP	Internally Displaced People
IMF	International Monetary Fund
IOM	International Organization for Migration
IRC	International Rescue Committee
JICA	Japan International Cooperation Agency
MAFS	Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security
MPM	Ministry of Petroleum and Mining
MSME	Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises
MTI	Ministry for Trade Industry
NHP	National Health Policy
NORAD	Norwegian Agency for Development Corporation
ODA	Official Development Assistance
OfD	Oil for Development
POC	Protection of Civilian
POC	Persons of Concern
R-ARCSS	Resolution of the Conflict in South Sudan
RCM	Refugee Coordination Model
ROI	Returns on Investments
SSNAP	South Sudan National Action Plan

SNSOP	Safety Net for Socio-Economic Project
SS	South Sudan
SSR	South Sudanese Refugees
TES	Transforming Education Summit
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
UNICEF	United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund
UNMISS	United Nations Mission in South Sudan
UNOPS	UN Office for Project Services
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
WB	World Bank
WFP	World Food Programme
WPS	Women's Peace and Security
WHO	World Health Organisation

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The study examines “The extent Foreign Aid in South Sudan takes a Conflict-Sensitive Approach to Development Interventions”. This chapter discusses the rationale for the study, the research methodology, and the framework of the study. Also, it examines conflict sensitivity and the principle of “Do No Harm” in the context of foreign aid and development intervention.

The Rationale of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine the extent foreign aid in South Sudan takes a conflict-sensitive approach to development interventions. It aims to identify and understand the causes of the South Sudan conflict, the factors that influence the conflict and the overall fragility of the state. It evaluates foreign aid in South Sudan and conflict-sensitive approaches to development intervention.

Development intervention in developing countries through international aid has been a global phenomenon within developed economies and organizations. While some countries have gained socioeconomic, environmental, and financial stability, others struggle with ethnic crises, human insecurity, food insecurity, political insecurity, and other economic and social vulnerabilities. According to the UNCTAD 2021 triennial review and its independent expert report on the Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC), the 46 Least Developed Countries are within the regions of Africa, Asia, the Caribbean, and the Pacific. And Africa hosts the highest number of fragile countries, including South Sudan.

As most insecurities exist within Africa causing conflicts and state fragility, in the last decade developed countries and organizations have taken a responsibility to support and provide aid to conflict-affected and fragile economies. As foreign aid is offered to countries like South Sudan consumed in ethnic, political, and socio-economic crises, donors must consider the context of the conflict in the economies they support. This includes existing crises and state fragility and ensuring that their activities do not cause further harm to sectors, the economy, the environment, and the people.

The focus of this research is.

1. To understand the concept of conflict sensitivity and ways humanitarian and development assistance avoids exacerbating existing conflict. Rather disengage and establish alternative systems to deal with the issues, and control the conflict (Anderson, 1999).
2. To assess conflict-sensitive approaches, frameworks and philosophies adopted for development interventions in South Sudan as a fragile state.
3. To identify risks associated with the lack of a conflict-sensitive approach to foreign aid.
4. To identify some benefits of adopting conflict-sensitive policies and frameworks to foreign aid in South Sudan.

Methodology

This section describes the method(s) adopted in evaluating the extent foreign aid in South Sudan takes a conflict-sensitive approach to development interventions. As several donors provide foreign aid, they must consider incorporating conflict sensitivity to development interventions and to what level. The method includes collecting secondary data to analyze existing literature on conflict in South Sudan, international assistance and aid experiences in South Sudan, and the impact on the state.

The decision to adopt secondary data collection was based on certain limitations to primary data collection. With access to existing data by previous authors through grey literature, inclusive information was obtained for evaluation. Some data sources include the *World Bank Development Indicators*, *NGOs (non-governmental organizations)*, *the UNCTADstat*, *Government and Social Development Resource Centre*, *the Department for International Development (DFID-UK aid)* and other viable sources.

The research philosophy adopted in this study is interpretivism, taking a qualitative approach, through subjective observation. This study was inductive, applying a bottom-up approach to obtain specific information and observations, and drawing on theories from the observations.

This study adopted an exploratory approach, as the data used was cross-sectional collected at one point in time and based on observation from a period. It aimed to conduct an in-depth evaluation of South Sudan as a republic, the crisis in South Sudan, effective design and conduct of conflict analysis, conflict-sensitive frameworks, implementation, and monitoring and control processes in development projects and programmes by foreign aid. This includes assessing

development projects and programmes and capacity for conflict-sensitive designs and frameworks. As well as tailored sustainable development approaches for beneficiaries, donors, and other stakeholders and a review of strategic and operational structures that update changing conflict dynamics and establish systems for detection and resolution.

Other limitations in the study include gaps in the data due to the unavailability of up-to-date data.

Conflict-Sensitivity- “Do No Harm”

According to Anderson (1999), in learning from diverse experiences, there is a clear realization of the uniqueness of each war. As each society has its history, culture, personages, values, and tensions and is unique, they share a commonality around conflict. Conflict often revolves around the struggle for either authority or resources. Therefore, starting any improvement through new or more resources, changing the decision-making process, or development and investment opportunities, would naturally disrupt perceived stability, peace, and conflict dynamics in the beneficiary country. For example, development aid can upset power relations, charge existing tensions, and foster unhealthy competition for resources between conflicting (ethnic) groups- instrumental to forms of corruption. Equivalently, if carefully planned and managed, foreign aid can help conflicting groups exist concurrently, and develop more nonprejudiced societies and civil communities.

Conflict sensitivity (“Do No Harm”) has been mainstreamed across the foreign aid sector for two decades or more. Conflict sensitivity has become a blanket term for a variance of analytical frameworks and tools adopted by humanitarian agencies and donors looking to adapt interventions to fragile and conflict-affected states (Schmiedl et al 2023). Haider (2014) defines conflict sensitivity as the capacity to understand the context in which the recipient environment runs and the interaction between the intervention and the context (how the intervention affects the context). And to act upon that understanding to avoid intensifying existing conflict, while enhancing more positive impacts. This includes establishing and adopting methods, aid policies and programmes to understand the context, and better assess the risks of operating in

these environments. As well as improve intervention sustainability and minimize potential risks to projects, partners, beneficiaries, and all other stakeholders. Saferworld (2015), more developed economies and international organizations have recognized the risks and potential for negative outcomes in foreign aid regardless of the intentions behind the aid provided. As a result, efforts to adopt a more conflict-sensitive approach have been further strengthened.

Understanding the Environment

The Department for International Development (DFID) (2010) states that having a deeper analysis and understanding of the context in conflict-affected and fragile situations is critical for developing and initiating the most effective responses. The importance of analysis and understanding of the environment, the context of the conflict and the dynamics of the conflict (at the national, regional, local, and sectoral levels) is to allow international aid efforts to be directed accurately towards the source of the conflict. And enhance the conflict sensitivity of development interventions. Also, this avoids reinforcing the crisis, promoting stability and peace, and maximizing aid and opportunities for growth.

According to the United Nations Sustainable Development Group (UNSDG) (2022), its integration of conflict-sensitivity into the UN program, building and achieving sustainable development goals and the three UN (human rights) pillars: *peace and security and development* in alignment with its conflict-sensitive approach to sustainable development and the “Do No Harm” principle consists of 4 key steps:

1. To understand the conflict and peace context through a conflict-sensitive and peacebuilding analysis to help prioritize and adjust activities, and address and mitigate drivers of conflict.
2. To analyze activities' interaction with peace and conflict. As situations evolve, there is a need to regularly consider if some activities may amplify the conflict dynamics and cause further apprehension or if these activities have the potential to create opportunities for development and peace.
3. To adapt activities and manage interactions. The United Nations (UN) entities encourage adaptation to minimize new risks, adjust responses and scale up activities as and when required.
4. To leverage opportunities for peace and development. The UN directs efforts to ease tensions, increase trust between the states and groups, and reduce the risk of outbreak, escalation, or continuous conflict.

International Alert (2023) defines conflict-sensitivity as the proactiveness and intentional steps to be conflict-sensitive in their approach to foreign aid and development programmes with a focus on minimizing the risks of harm and actively contributing to promoting peace. Making Sense of Localization in Sudan (2023) states that conflict sensitivity seeks to inform and enable effective engagement in the relationship between the foreign aid donors and the foreign aid system in the country. This indicates increasing awareness and efforts towards a conflict-sensitive approach to foreign aid and development interventions.

The conflict in South Sudan is primarily ethnic-related since the division of South and North Sudan, there has been a struggle for land, power, leadership, and other resources, affecting the

country's social, economic, financial, and human capital development. Therefore, progress made through foreign aid and development interventions in South Sudan is quickly disrupted and overridden by the existence or start of a crisis and violent conflict. Essentially, violent conflict and issues in conflict-affected areas upset the potential for donor organizations and countries to effectively access the vulnerability of communities, and compromise efforts to go beyond immediate responses to more long-term development. According to Saferworld (2015), 85% of (global) relief workers reported their experience and involvement in emergency work that was implicated in existing conflicts and caused further conflicts in some situations.

Adopting a conflict-sensitive approach can be a reduced-cost and effective means of supporting organizations to steer difficult contexts in ways that can minimize potential negatives and maximize positive impacts of foreign economic and financial aid and peace. All these are presupposed on the understanding that the design, integration, and implementation of interventions have the potential to reduce, sustain, amplify, or trigger conflict. Therefore, careful analysis and adaptation of programme design are needed for foreign aid.

Undoubtedly, the goals of foreign aid and development intervention efforts are to improve the quality of life in developing countries and promote peace, it could sometimes do more harm than good. Thereby, triggering conflict and state fragility. According to Finckenstein (2021), fragile and conflict-affected states indicate unresolved conflict. In crisis, it is common for international donors to promise money in return for reforms that often lack proper oversight and implementation. In the short term, this collapses due to a lack of focus, poor strategic planning, poor management systems, bad leadership, and corruption.

The United Nations Peace Building Support (UNPBS) and Safer World (2013) assess the relationship and complexities between political violence, ethnicity, and inequality through 'horizontal' inequality as a driver of conflict. And how horizontal inequalities increase the risk of violent conflict. Thorp et al. (2006) claim that the degree of inequality based on ethnicity is highly relevant to the degree of violence that results when conflict is instigated. These inequalities and violent conflicts, and the relationship between them can hold back development. The United Nations Peace Building Support and Safer World (2015) calls for addressing these elements in development frameworks.

Figure 1: **Horizontal Inequality Framework**

Source: **Research Gate**

The UN Press Release (2023) argues that foreign aid to fragile states tends to delay the potential for a transition from an economic crisis, and potentially increase forms of ethnic rivalry relating to recipients of aid and benefits, political control, financial instability, as well as corruption. In most fragile and conflict-affected countries, the political leader controls all aspects of the economy, particularly financial and economic infrastructures. So, the kind of leadership in place affects intervention from foreign aid organizations and countries and the ability for development. While “Do No Harm” is still often used in place of conflict sensitivity, the latter is still the most well-known and widely adopted.

Harms caused by not adopting a conflict-sensitive approach to foreign aid and development interventions include:

1. **Access Challenges:** Political, military, and other major actors within conflict-affected states may limit access to locations that require aid or insist on control of access, therefore manipulating development activities.
2. **Financial Risks:** There is high inflation, volatility, and insufficiency due to corruption. The financial uncertainty and instability continuously affect aid provided and other development efforts. This can affect the decision-making process of the local stakeholders and continuously diminish efforts by donors and development support.
3. **High Prevalence of Conflict Outbreaks:** This is due to feelings of vulnerability, poor and ineffective communication amongst stakeholders, conflicting stakeholder interests and influence levels, escalation, and recurrence of conflict, theft and mismanagement of resources leading to increased deaths.

4. ***Deepened Corruption:*** Systems in conflict-affected states are often controlled by autonomy, allowing the head of state to make autonomous decisions on all matters in the state. This type of leadership tends to make national decisions only in favour of comrades, especially in fragile situations centred around ethnic and political rivalry.

The next chapter discusses South Sudan and the conflict in South Sudan from the perspective of various scholars.

Chapter 2

Introduction

This chapter examines existing data and theories on South Sudan and the conflict in South Sudan with a focus on the cause, the impacts and how it affects the state's fragility. It discusses the present state of the conflict, the factors that influence the conflict, the ways it minimises development opportunities for growth capacity, peace agreement initiatives and conflict sensitivity of development intervention.

South Sudan

South Sudan is rich in lush savannas, swamplands, and rainforests, and is home to different wildlife. Before 2011, South Sudan was one with North Sudan. Its population is predominantly African in culture with a blend of Christian and (largely) Muslim citizens. In the early 19th century, while Sudan was under British-Egyptian rule, southern Sudan was plundered into slavery while the north resisted. Then British energies were directed more toward the modernization of the North and the South struggled to maintain order. This led to conflict between North and South for decades.

South Sudan became a Republic in 2011 and the youngest nation in the world. Although the world's youngest country, it has a long history of conflict. Its independence was accompanied by underdevelopment and challenges such as decades of intense conflict and huge human costs. Studies suggest that the war in South Sudan is recorded as one of the world's worst conflicts (United Nations & Global Focus, 2018). With high exposure to human rights violations, ranging

from corruption to inter-ethnic violence, and sexual abuse. As well as very little or no assistance from the judicial system and the public service, or infrastructure for the most vulnerable (Spaulding et al., 2011).

Currently, the capital of South Sudan is Juba with 10 states and 3 administrative areas. Bahr el Ghazal, Greater Upper Nile, and the Equatoria, designed from the previously 32 states. All three areas are oil producing which accounts for about 98% of South Sudan's export revenue (Falk, 2020).

Figure 2: South Sudan in Focus

Source: VOA Africa (Falk, 2020)

South Sudan has two prominent ethnic groups, the Dinka and Nuer, amongst other tribes. The Dinka and Nuer are the two rival pastoralist groups, competing over pastures and water for their livestock and other Agricultural activities. This has been a major cause of resource conflicts and

cattle raiding, as well as clashes which have led to massive numbers of fatalities. The dynamics have been intensified in the last 30 years by increased drought in the country (Richardson, 2011). In 2013, the former vice president Riek Machar, a Nuer was dismissed by South Sudan's president, a Dinka which acted as a catalyst for extreme violence and deaths (Climate Diplomacy, 2013).

Figure 3: South Sudan Ethnic Composition

Source: Britannica

The Conflict in South Sudan

Alex de Waal (2016) suggests that South Sudan's civil war is the result of a weak institutionalized state. Five years after independence, South Sudan is faced with a civil war that has killed over 50,000 and displaced 1.6 million people. Ethnicity played a huge role in the breaking out of the civil war, due to President Salva Kiir's accusation of former vice president Reik Machar plotting a coup d'état.

Alex de Waal (2016) claimed that things progressed easily from a political crisis to war, not because of ethnic divisions, but rather because of the poor institutionalized military system. With a collection of militias organized based on personal loyalty to its commander, the army is essentially based on ethnicity. Noel's (2016) analysis of the post-independence conflict in South Sudan, is that it is based on a combination of self-serving actions from international indulgence and an excess of money and other funds. And that was a catalyst for very bad judgment on the part of the country's political leaders.

One major error as a fragile state was to cut off 98% of its source of revenue for six months, because of its dispute with north Sudan. The Government of South Sudan (GoSS) is experiencing a struggle over legitimacy and monopoly on the use of force. The moment a state loses control of its monopoly over the use of force is the moment the state dies (Nyadera 2021: Adams 2000). Scholars claim that South Sudanese elites at every level use force and the threat of force in their daily political engagements and bargaining to produce a monetized system and militarized tribalism.

The situation in South Sudan is more disturbing as the use of force is not solely in the hands of the present government since the rival has significant support, legitimacy and a solid army that

has control over various parts of the country. Then there is its poor institutionalization as a nation that allows groups to be organized around ethnicity, the president, the militias and the Mathiang Anyoor (the brown caterpillar), responsible for the massacres in Juba in the 2013 conflict. The conflict in South Sudan has displaced over 3.9 million people, with over 1 million refugees hosted by Uganda- mostly women and children (Conciliation Resources, 2017).

Dermawan et al. (2019) further discussed several theories on the challenges of the conflict, and conflict resolution in South Sudan, in connection to its impact on human security. Particularly the economic, health, food, environmental, community issues, and political insecurity. The ethnic and intra-state conflict in South Sudan continues to diminish foreign aid aimed towards next-level development in the state. Dermawan et al. (2019) claim that ethnic identity and lack of it has a grip on the state which causes tensions between ethnic groups and reflects poorly on the state's political scene. And affects over 20% of its population, and causes thousands of deaths (British Government, 2001). This emphasizes the human security element in the conflict and identifies the impact of the ethnic conflict in South Sudan. This further elaborates on how development interventions and other infrastructures can increase state fragility.

Conflict Factors

Dermawan et al. (2019) and Douma (2003) discussed certain factors that have affected the South Sudan conflict, the impact levels, and opportunities for resolution. These conflict factors include the,

1. **Trigger factor.** These are events that increase the conflict. The trigger factor in the South Sudan war is the leadership and struggle for power. The struggle for power (political and otherwise) between the two major ethnic groups in power.
2. **Pivotal factor.** This is the core of any conflict- the reason for the conflict. To end the conflict is to resolve its pivotal factor. In South Sudan, the pivotal factor is its unstable ethnic and government system because of the tensions between the two major ethnic groups, the Dinka, and the Nuer. The oldest and second oldest ethnic group in South Sudan, consecutively.
3. **Mobilizing factor.** These are actors that influence the direction of the conflict. Those whose actions have a major impact by either maximizing or minimizing the conflict. Such as the leaders of the Dinka and Nuer ethnic groups, the military, and the Commander in Chief.
4. **Aggravating factor.** These are factors that influence both the pivotal and the mobilizing factors. The study suggests that in South Sudan, the aggravating factor is the need for leadership and who owns power. A combination of individuals and groups in government, and those who wish to be in the government.

Based on theories that conflict occurs because of differences in interests, the parties involved and their actions, the lack of effective mechanisms to manage conflict could lead to impacts such as war. This leads to non-traditional insecurities, that affect human security separately from the traditional form of security (Smith, 2004 & Douma, 2003). Dermawan (2019) looks at the fragility in South Sudan particularly from the human insecurity perspective and its impact on foreign aid through conflict resolution and other development interventions. Nyadera (2018) argues that in most developing countries, the unstable government tends to maximize conflict between the warring ethnic groups because of high corruption and as they struggle for power-affecting almost every aspect of state affairs. While Nyadera (2018) assumes that ethnicity is an important variable, the pivotal factor causing the conflict in South Sudan is its poor institutionalized political system and the chaotic power struggle. This includes the country's oil resources and weapons distribution.

As the office of the president in South Sudan holds the most authority, the president controls all the nation's resources, the military, the financial sector, and other aspects of the nation's economy. Thus, the need by the protagonists to dominate and achieve more, and other personal and ethnic interests is the power struggle experienced in South Sudan. Nyaderas' opinion is that ethnicity is the mobilizing weapon used by conflicting parties to win the conflict.

The Intensity of the South Sudan Crisis

In December 2013, beginning with inter-ethnic tensions, violence occurred between the sitting government (the Dinkas') and the opposition (the Nuers'). This affected South Sudan's human security and increased the need for immediate international interventions (Dessaiegn, 2017). However, because of the country's ethnic and political rivalry, struggle for governing power, and intra-state wars, foreign aid, conflict resolution and other development efforts in South Sudan have been made fragile and so far, unsuccessful.

The impact of the conflict in South Sudan has not gone unnoticed by the international community. Countries and organizations have embarked on a series of mediation and negotiation processes in South Sudan (Nyadera, 2021). Jok (2015) and Nyadera (2021) confirm that several protocols and agreements signed by representatives of the North and the South between 2002 and 2004 processes have led up to the signing of the Comprehensive Peace Agreement (CPA) in January 2005. Unfortunately, the most recent peace agreement like many others set by the committee for March 2015 in South Sudan has failed. A new agreement was drafted in June 2015 to end the ongoing conflict. Before then, in 2013- a few weeks into the war, the United Nations (UN) recorded an estimated thousands of deaths and about 120,000 others displaced. Among these were 63,000 others seeking shelter at the United Nations Peacebuilding Base (UNOCHA 2013; Nyadera 2021).

South Sudan's economy has become heavily militarized. Podder, (2014) argues that the militarization of ethnic groups in the South obtained momentum in the post-independence period. An example is the use of child soldiers and the formation of self-protection brigades in

the form of non-state armed groups, such as the 'Arrow Boys'. To show the intensity of the South Sudan war, the Secretary-General sanctioned the transfer of troops from other conflict regions in the African Union (AU) and the United Nations Hybrid Operation in Darfur (UNAMID). Aid agencies recorded over 50,000 deaths (Martell, 2016); (Nyadera 2021).

Four years into the war, there was a hike in the number of displaced people by over 2.3 million. Sadly, the initial split in the Sudan People Liberation Movement was between achieving a united Sudan and an independent South, supported by Machar. But the focus changed as the split intensified pressure from the Khartoum military and the loss of the Ethiopian government's support. At this point, it became a matter of self-preservation and other ethnic objectives (Jok & Hutchinson, 1999); (Giessmann et al., 2018). Due to extremely high levels of militarization in South Sudan, the conflict took a qualitatively different angle from earlier disputes to no-holds-barred military assaults on Dinka and Nuer's unarmed civilian populations.

After the coup, decades of politics in Khartoum were dominated by power struggles between Bashir and Tarubi, those who supported the vision of a 'New Sudan' and southerners wanting a clear commitment to independence. It became clear that most of the post-independent conflict in South Sudan was because of internal power struggles within ruling parties, opponents, and a vicious cycle of rebellion around disputes over resources, mainly oil.

Before the country could enjoy its independence, the civil war happened. There was insufficient time to establish mechanisms and institutions to handle and minimize the effects of war. With a state too fragile to manage conflict or avoid the war, some challenges faced include.

1. The limited budget required for adequate crisis response in 2017 was about 1.7 billion US Dollars, projected to support over 7 million beneficiaries.
2. Renewed violence and dissatisfied civilian opposition groups and political parties.
3. Women's activities in dialogues were downplayed and generally undervalued.
4. Negotiations about the Nile divisions, sharing parts of the Nile, and negotiating the distribution of the use of the Nile waters for irrigation, hydropower, and other development projects.

Alongside the war, the GoSS has been accused of corrupt actions in the process, including illegal detentions, restriction of media freedom, repression of critics and crippling the economy. The situation in South Sudan has been worsened by a severe famine that lasted more than six months, unchecked violent crimes against humanity and other political and financial crimes. As shown in Figure 4 this has led to a cumulative loss in the growth rate of per-capita real GDP was 86.5%, resulting in an accumulated loss in the per-capita GDP of 7,070 USD and an accumulated loss in the aggregate GDP of 8.1 billion USD.

Figure 4: South Sudan GDP Per Capita 2008- 2023

Source: World Bank, 2023

Scarcity and increases in prices led to reduced consumption, which in turn led to increased poverty (IMF 2019b; World Bank, 2017b). In a report by Frontier Economics in collaboration with the Center for Conflict Resolution, Mercy Corps (2018) shows about 1 million IDPs, over 2 million fled South Sudanese, and 1 in 3 refugees in South Sudan. An estimated USD 20 billion has been spent by the United Nations on peacebuilding efforts in South Sudan since 2014, with slow achievement in sustainable peace (Nyadera, 2021 & Rolandsen, 2015).

The ethnic and political war in South Sudan has led to more crimes than recorded including Gender-Based Violence (GBV), rape, attacks directed at civilians, arson, murder, and kidnapping-aiders have been attacked; food trucks looted by locals and different groups. Children eligible to be in school are not enrolled, and farmers and other workers are constantly fleeing for safety and survival. Estimating the cost of the conflict on economic outcomes in South Sudan involves many problems, including damages to lives and properties, aggregated issues, and damages to various sectors (Abadie and Gardezabal, 2003). More than 600 political violence events and nearly 2,800 reported deaths across Sudan since the full-scale war between the Sudanese Armed Forces (SAF) and the paramilitary Rapid Support Forces (RSF) since the 15th of April 2023 (*Sudan Situation Update: June 2023*). Despite considerable peace agreements between the warring parties, the fights have continued.

Recent data from Concern Worldwide US (2021) shows that 8.3 million South Sudanese people need humanitarian assistance. 2.3 million refugees, 1.7 million IDPs, 1.4 million children, 483,000 malnourished women, 809,000 flood survivors from the May 2021 flood and 34,000 people displaced in the Protection of Civilian (POC) sites. Before the 2013 conflict outbreak, many were optimistic about the development and progress in South Sudan, but a new crisis started in December 2013. This created a domino effect of humanitarian emergencies.

The next chapter discusses foreign aid actors and activities in South Sudan.

Chapter 3

Introduction

This chapter examines country and organisation-led foreign aid actors and donors in South Sudan and their foreign aid philosophies. It discusses development areas and how aid policies and activities affect development intervention. Furthermore, it examines the extent countries and organisations' international aid consider conflict-sensitivity in their development interventions.

Foreign Aid Actors in South Sudan

Over time, there has been an emergence of various official foreign aid and development actors across the globe. Development agencies, banks, international institutions, states, and local authorities. At the international level, there are the: World Bank (IDA and IBRD), the United Nations agencies (UNICEF, UNDP, UNESCO, UNHCR, and others), the European Union, and the African Union. At the regional level, there are regional development banks such as the African Development Bank (AfDB), Asian Development Bank (ADB), Inter-American Development Bank (IDB), and other vertical funds. Each plays a significant role in developing or conflict-affected countries and economies (Agence Francaise de Developpement, 2023).

In 1970, members of the Development Assistance Committee of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development agreed to provide 0.7 per cent of their wealth and gross national income towards public development aid. A commitment that was then renewed in 2015. Amongst these countries, the USA, the United Kingdom, Norway, and Japan have

exceeded the mark and reached 0.17 and 0.20 per cent respectively (Agence Francaise de Developpement, 2023).

Foreign Aid Actors and Participation in South Sudan’s Conflict and Post-Conflict Era

South Sudan's vulnerability to global warming and natural disasters, alongside continuous war amounts to its fragility. This compromises its potential for recovery and further undermines development efforts in the State. As shown in Figure 5, the trend from independence to war and attempts at peace agreements continues to negatively impact the country’s GDP.

Figure 5: GDP Index 2011- 2021

Source: IMF Country Report 2022

Country-Led Foreign Aid

The report on external actors in South Sudan stated that the Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD) has taken the lead in external efforts to end the persistent conflict in the country Mustasa and Virk (2017). The Troika, comprising the United States of America, Britain, and Norway are key players that have supported the IGAD-led peace process and have been committed to bringing back and implementing the South Sudan peace agreement. With the continuous conflict, dysfunctional government system, human insecurity and high rate of displacement, South Sudan relies majorly on foreign aid to revive the country.

The United States of America (USA)

The U.S. government has provided more than USD 9.5 billion to South Sudan, mostly coordinated by the South Sudan Humanitarian Response Plan (SSHRP) and other development priorities. The U.S. foreign policy is “to speak softly and carry a big stick.” Its economic strength possesses a form of soft power, contributing to its ability to have its way and achieve outcomes most favourable to Americans. Thus, its foreign aid policies are usually in the areas of supporting its *national security* and *commercial and economic interests*. It is in this context that the U.S., despite the challenges and setbacks experienced in Juba has remained one of the most relevant foreign aid actors in South Sudan.

In the 90s, Washington played a critical role in the humanitarian aid to South Sudan, exceeding 12 billion dollars in expenditure. The U.S. was instrumental in the 2005 Comprehensive Peace Agreement negotiations between South Sudan and the Sudan People’s Liberation Movement/Army (SPLM/A). This included one of the largest political organisations and rebel

groups formed in South Sudan since 1983. The U.S. served as the agreement's most influential external guarantor (Mustasa and Virk, 2017).

In the run-up to the Southern referendum in January 2011, Washington provided major support to the Thabo-Mbeki-led African Union High-Level Implementation Panel (AUHIP), influencing, and serving as a valuable link between the AUHIP and the United Nations Security Council. After South Sudan's independence in July 2011, the U.S., the EU, and African countries significantly invested in capacity development in South Sudan (Mustasa and Virk, 2017, p. 30). The financing ranged from education and health care programmes to infrastructure development and training and development for government officials towards improving management and leadership capacity. In 2012, South Sudan received about USD 1 billion in humanitarian aid, with more than a quarter of that from the U.S.

As shown in diagram 6, in January 2013 Juba unceremoniously decided to shut down oil production because it disagreed with Khartoum. The U.S. substituted and regulated its aid and development programmes to suit the conditions in South Sudan and proceeded to organise a donor conference to support the country in handling the impact of the revenue cuts (International Monetary Fund, 2020) and (International Crisis Group, 2021). Between 2014 and 2017, the U.S. provided a humanitarian investment of more than USD 2.1 billion, making it the largest single donor of humanitarian aid to South Sudan (Mustasa and Virk, 2017).

Figure 6: **Estimated SS Oil Revenue 2011-2020 (Billions of USD)**

Source: **International Crisis Group (2021)**

According to the Office of Press Relations USAID (2023) press release and the announcement by the U.S. Ambassador to South Sudan Michael J. Adler in Bahr el Ghazal State on the U.S. humanitarian assistance to South Sudan, new additional funding of USD 288 million for humanitarian support was provided in 2011 because of the extreme food insecurity and malnutrition. The current 288 million dollars in additional funding allowed USAID’s partnership with the UN World Food Programme (WFP) to tackle critical humanitarian needs and support over 2.2 million of the world's most food-insecure nations. Aside from supporting and providing life-saving food assistance, the funding aimed to support health care services and nutrition for the crisis-affected populace in the country. This includes movement and management support to humanitarian cargo and personnel in inaccessible areas in dire need.

Despite the continuous violent conflict, declining economic conditions, successive years of flooding, and the global food crisis and other issues, including interference with the delivery of

humanitarian assistance in South Sudan, the U.S. continues to provide their support to significantly minimise the suffering of South Sudanese people. However, the crisis is further complicated by local political actors who seem unconcerned by the sufferings of the people. And often make promises of reconciliation before eventually retreating into armed conflict.

As the U.S. claims to provide humanitarian assistance based on the needs of the beneficiaries, it acknowledges the human factors that pose a threat to opportunities for support and development in South Sudan. This includes subnational violence that has been a challenge and harms humanitarian access. While the U.S. considers the context of the conflict environment in South Sudan, these human factors play a critical role in the extent the U.S. takes a conflict-sensitive approach to its development intervention.

The United Kingdom

As one of the world's leaders in foreign aid within the last 5 years, Britain's foreign aid has reached millions across the world, including South Sudan. It has supported 11 million children to school and over 60 million access to clean water, sanitation, and better hygiene conditions, amongst other development efforts. As the world faces new challenges like state fragility and a rise in global insecurity, there is a risk of rising conflict in previously secure countries. Thus, the UK's foreign aid philosophy on *global poverty elimination, Colonialism (soft power)* and most importantly, *economic advancement*.

While the government is committed to supporting economic development in fragile states, it is also firmly interested in its national interest. Also, ensures that the support it provides creates

Value for Money, and greater opportunities for British businesses and maintains her position as a global leader (Department for International Development, 2015).

During the 2017 Department of International Development (DfID) press release, in addition to the UK-funded food aid distributed by the WFP in South Sudan, the British Minister for Africa announced GBP 52 million worth of humanitarian package for South Sudan. This was channelled towards helping refugees, IDPs, and other groups that were affected by the ongoing armed conflict in South Sudan.

According to the Minister for Africa for the Foreign Commonwealth Office, Rory Stewart, *“the people of South Sudan have continued to suffer various human insecurities, lack of human rights and humanitarian crisis because of the ongoing conflict in the country. Causing the damage of the war to affect many other regions.”* The support package provided by Britain was aimed at helping South Sudan and thousands of IDPs with basic life-sustaining resources.

Between 2017 and 2022, Britain provided about GBP 52 million worth of aid to South Sudan, with a breakdown of GBP 19 million to provide shelter, education, sanitary provision, food, and other essentials to over 50,000 South Sudanese Refugees (SSR). GBP 15 million to provide food assistance to 950,000 SSR in Uganda. GBP 8 million towards healthcare, malnutrition treatment and clean water for 450,000 SSR in Ethiopia. GBP 10 million was spent to help about 500,000 South Sudanese with a variety of interventions including shelter, medicine, emergency food, improved health, and sanitation. And seeds, tools, and fishing apparatus to help families maintain their livelihood.

Britain's support strategy includes providing support workers with the necessities and about 300 British military manpower to work on vital roads and infrastructure in adverse conditions. Its effort to take a conflict-sensitive approach to international development is its clear statement of expectations for progress from peace processes, involvement, and encouragement of all parties to end hostilities, stop all barriers and allow humanitarian access to help victims of the conflict. And ultimately, grow to more advanced development in the country.

Norway

Norway's foreign aid and development policy is *strategic realism*, as it gradually builds a more stable governmental capacity and a seat at the world's table (Kvelland, 2013). As Norway gained membership in NATO and its foreign policy gradually shifted from international idealism, it became a strong patron of human rights and development. Although disappointed about the sufferings and economic decline of South Sudan, and its belief that the conflict and issues of the country are mainly man-made, Norway has been a dedicated partner to South Sudan for the last 50 years.

In the Minister for Development Aid, Anne Beathe's most recent visit to Juba during the peace agreement dialogue, there were discussions with representatives from development organizations, agencies, civil societies, and individuals affected by the South Sudan crisis. Despite Norway's position on the cause of the South Sudan crisis and its high-priority status in recent years, Norway continues to support South Sudan (Ventures Africa, 2019). The most recent contribution brings Norway's total foreign aid to South Sudan to an estimated NOK 172 million (UN, 2019).

As one of the most Norway-funded countries and as shown in Figure 7, South Sudan received up to NOK 427 million in 2015, following the 578 million from the Norwegian Directorate for Aid and Development (Norad), the centre of development cooperation in 2011.

Figure 7: Norwegian Official Development Aid

Source: Norwegian Aid Statistics (2015)

In its effort to adopt a conflict-sensitive approach to its development efforts, Norway channels support through local aid and development actors in South Sudan as this should ordinarily help with fair distribution and provide a more rapid and effective response to the direct needs of the people. As such, Norway continues to urge local authorities and development aid actors to cooperate and monitor closely, to ensure foreign aid provided is accessible to all, especially those most in need (Ventures Africa, 2019).

With its history in oil extraction and development assistance, Norway has been committed to elucidating the dispute between North and South Sudan by helping South Sudan manage its natural resources and develop the capacity essential to its development (Kvelland, 2013).

These include the following initiatives.

1. Oil for Development (OfD)

As a major beneficiary of the OfD program, pre-independence South Sudan received a major increase in its allocation which was meant to serve as an economic buffer for the new state. The operative objective was to assist developing countries with petroleum resources like South Sudan to generate economic growth and promote state welfare and environmental sustainability.

2. Capacity Building

The Norwegian Agency for Development Corporation (NORAD) funded three capacity-building sub-programmes in South Sudan. The aim was to develop the tertiary education system that has been destroyed by years of crisis, and ultimately reduce poverty in the state. Other project objectives included filling capacity gaps in the government sector, especially the democratic government (Jávorka et al., 2018). Other capacity-building activities include resource and environmental management, aimed at developing the capacity of journalists to cover oil-related issues, increase transparency and maximize public awareness of the Ministry of Petroleum and Mining (MPM) and its management. Considering oil distribution and management is a major cause of the conflict in South Sudan, this level of capacity development was relevant to taking a conflict-sensitive approach to development intervention. Ultimately, this was meant to establish

a wider level of capacity and increase oil revenue to reflect overall economic revenue-advantageous to South Sudanese people (Kvelland, 2013).

The Sudan Post (2021) reports the Norwegian Ambassador to South Sudan, Siv Kaspersen's statement, "*Norway reaffirms its commitment to support the ongoing revitalized peace agreement's implementation in South Sudan.*" As part of a broader Peace Research Institute Oslo (PRIO) initiative, South Sudan participated in disarmament negotiations as a condition required for peace (Marsh, 2022).

Despite active efforts to incorporate a conflict-sensitive approach in development implementations, Norway amongst other countries finds itself dealing with exploitative and corrupt behaviours that negate efforts to adopt a conflict-sensitive approach and provide support. This increased the human and financial cost of foreign aid access. Fundamentally, to end the hostilities and welcome economic growth in South Sudan, there is a need to increase inclusivity in political processes, to enable a more functional government system and service delivery.

Japan

After the incorporation of the **human security** and **individual-focused** philosophy as the core significance of security by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) in 1994, it was then sanctioned by Japan as a major focus of its foreign policy. Developed and implemented through Japan's ODA projects in 2011, Japan established peacebuilding and diplomatic relations with South Sudan- shifting towards its foreign policy agenda to be a more proactive defence and impact on human security. (Tana, 2021d).

In applying the *Neoclassical Realism* framework, Tana (2021) argues the high relevance of the human security focus of Japanese foreign policy despite its alternate *strategic orientation*. Japan in its 'quiet diplomacy' contributed to South Sudan peacebuilding through the United Nations Mission in South Sudan (UNMISS)- largely driven by Japan's principles of human security. Japan strongly relies on its non-military approach to peacebuilding based on human security, with a lot of its contributions centred around development assistance to countries like South Sudan.

In reinforcing the "All Japan Approach", the strategic alignment of the military, the ODA projects, and the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) and NGO activities, Japan aimed to develop the connection between peacebuilding using temporary means and development assistance using extending measures (Uesugi, 2014).

According to Tana (2021) in 2012, the first grant agreements between the Government of the Republic of South Sudan (GoRSS) and the (JICA) were signed to assist with three basic economic and social infrastructure projects in Juba:

1. *The development and supply of clean water in Juba.*
2. *The establishment of the Juba River Port.*
3. *The construction of the Nile River Bridge ("Freedom Bridge").*

Beyond the development of the basic economy and social infrastructures was the improvement of living standards supported by the JICA in its interest towards strengthening *education, healthcare, trade and other technical training*, and the development of alternative sectors such

as *Agriculture*. The objective was to reduce South Sudan's dependence on the oil industry whilst developing governance and security through these projects (Tana, 2021).

Before the December 2013 crisis, Japan had begun implementing various development intervention opportunities such as road rehabilitation in Juba, the water purification plant in Juba and the personnel development project in collaboration with a Japanese NGO- the Japan Center for Conflict Prevention (Uesugi 2014, p.230) and (Tana, 2021). After the 2013 crisis and as the situation became more volatile, Japan made moves to withdraw direct contact with the situation. However, as shown in Figure 8, it continued to assist South Sudan with various exports and supplies. According to the WFP (2014) report, Japan contributed USD 4.6 million to the UN WFP's work in South Sudan to help those affected by the conflict and support communities with food security.

Figure 8: **Japan Exports to South Sudan**

Source: **Trading Economics, 2023**

Scholars argued that Japan's commitment to play an active role in South Sudan was mostly motivated by political and economic sentiments, competition with China and the rest of the world and its realist considerations. Although the Japanese foreign aid policy barely takes a conflict-sensitive approach, it has been one of the most recent and longest peacekeeping missions in South Sudan (Tana, 2021).

Organization-Led Aid

This section examines organizations, agencies, and civil societies' aid in South Sudan since its independence and its attempt to emerge as a new nation. It highlights aid policies and the level of conflict sensitivity in their development interventions.

The United Nations

According to the UN (2020) Charter Statement, its core objective and policy are ***to deliver humanitarian aid, achieve international collaboration and solve global economic, cultural, social, and humanitarian issues***. Since the incorporation of the human security approach to aid and development of beneficiary countries, the UN has supported international aid through the UNMISS and vice versa. In 2011, the UN Security Council admitted South Sudan as a member with the mandate to support the GoSS in peace consolidation and foster lasting state-building and economic development. This included the call on the GoSS to strengthen the prevention and response to GBV, accelerate policies that effectively address conflict-related sexual abuse and ensure accountability for offenders (UNICEF, South Sudan, 2023).

The Russian Federation encouraged a close involvement of local authorities in resolving South Sudan's intercommunal conflict, stating that "it would build the country's potential and strengthen its unified armed forces", as a more constructive form of peacekeeping dialogue (UNICEF, South Sudan, 2023). So far, the UN Office for Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (UNOCHA) totals about 192 organisations currently responding to the crisis in South Sudan with emergency programs (Yayboke, 2018). Through the UN Central Emergency Response Fund (CERF) and in collaboration with Norway, humanitarian aid worth NOK 11 million has been provided to SSR in neighboring countries. Following the 2013 outbreak, the UN released USD 15 million from its Rapid Response Fund for urgent foreign aid.

According to the UNMISS (2017), the organisation's civilians, police and military personnel perform their duties within the mandate of the UN Security Council- in consideration of the conflict context of the environment and providing aid, as categorised under four pillars.

1. *Civilian Protection.*
2. *Creating Access and Favourable Conditions for Humanitarian Assistance.*
3. *Support for the Implementation of Renewed Peace Agreement and Progress.*
4. *Human Rights Monitoring and Investigating.*

In line with development initiatives and programmes, the Ministry of Trade and Industry (MTI) of South Sudan in partnership with the UN Development Programme in 2022, launched the E-commerce Hub in Juba. The E-commerce for South Sudan Project is supported by the AfDB, the Netherlands Embassy, the Enhanced Integrated Framework (EIF) and the MTI. The project is aimed at creating employment opportunities through the digitalisation of the economy, in

support of the Revised National Development Strategy 2021-2024 implementation (UNDP, 2022). Some of the objectives of the South Sudan E-commerce Project include.

1. A nationwide creation of opportunities for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) and development opportunities for women and youth interested in participating in emerging markets.
2. A contribution to private sector development, to promote entrepreneurship and create jobs.
3. Opportunities for connection, to associate manufacturers and producers with other members of the value chain across businesses.
4. Opportunities for Information and Communication Technology (ICT) capacity development, digital marketing, data analytics, procurement and merchandising, social media marketing, online store management and other basic ICT skills and upskilling.
5. An established online space to promote business opportunities and sell products, as South Sudan’s first-ever online marketplace platform.

Table 1: **UN South Sudan Intervention Milestones 2011-2020**

2011	The support of South Sudan’s shift from conflict to recovery and development.
2013	The Return and Rehabilitation of Refugees and IDPs and Peace promotion, recovery, sustainable development, and lifesaving support to South Sudan citizens.
2018	The participation in South Sudan’s peace agreement.

2020

The support framework focused on the recovery and resilience of the South Sudanese people.

The UN claimed to prioritize conflict-sensitive approaches to aid and development intervention through the promotion of peace agreements and conflict recovery exercises.

United Nations International Children’s Emergency Fund (UNICEF)

As an organization under the UN General Assembly, the UNICEF policy is founded on the Convention on the Rights of the Child. Its core objective is *to establish children’s rights as lasting ethical principles and global standards of conduct towards children* (UNICEF, 2023).

UNICEF works with country and organization donors to fund activities to support the most disadvantaged children and young people in South Sudan. In 2021, UNICEF appealed for USD 180 million to provide aid to the most vulnerable children in areas of Education, Food and Nutrition, Vaccines, Emergency Relief, Water, Sanitation and Climate Change Protection. Nakashian and UNICEF (2023) reported that according to the Global Partnership for Education (GPE), the education system in South Sudan is indicative of low investment and low capacity.

A major framework for education by UNICEF in South Sudan is to position early childhood education in the country’s education sector plans, in the context of the existing conflict. UNICEF supported the Department of Early Childhood Education to organise funding and resources to incorporate early child education in sectoral planning and to strengthen capacity and advocacy in 2022. In the same year, a Pre-Primary Subsector Analysis Tool was used to outline existing

strengths and weaknesses and recognise available resources to support an environment for the pre-primary subsector. Taking into consideration the South Sudan conflict-affected environment and context and incorporating a critical level of conflict sensitivity in its techniques (Nakashian & UNICEF, 2023).

In January 2023, a nationwide policy, strategy, and implementation to provide pre-primary education was accomplished for South Sudan and was further validated in May 2023, for inclusion into the new education sector plan for the country. UNICEF's focus for the new strategy, aligned with the General Education Strategic Plan 2023-2028, is to ensure continuous learning during, post-conflict and other emergencies. Ultimately, this improved understanding of the significance of developing the Education sector with an increase in budget allocation of 13.6% of the total 2022 education budget.

Beyond the larger programme activities, UNICEF supports and performs smaller project activities that include building classrooms, educating, and training teachers, developing, and printing textbooks and working with communities to promote and encourage South Sudan parents and guardians to enroll their children in school.

Other information on UNICEF programme activities to protect the rights of children and youth in South Sudan includes.

Child Protection

This includes the end of child recruitment into armed groups, and partnerships with other agencies and donors to ensure reunions between South Sudanese children and their families. Collaborations with community leaders to stop child marriages, prevent GBV and establish a safe space for survivors, and those of other forms of abuse (UNICEF South Sudan, 2021a).

Food and Nutrition

In 2021 UNICEF had a 95.6% recovery rate for children with extreme malnutrition outpatient therapeutic programme (UNICEF South Sudan, 2021). Between 2010 and 2021, UNICEF invested largely in promoting breastfeeding and nutrition counseling. This led to a 50% reduction in advanced malnutrition among children. UNICEF in collaboration with the Water, Sanitation and Health (WASH) and the health sector further reduced health risks and improved access to a healthier start in life.

Health

UNICEF has worked toward helping South Sudanese children stay healthy, but with poor access to health care and limited health workers, the country remains one of the worst on the global health indicator.

UNICEF has been educating local health workers to provide health services to South Sudanese people during and post-conflict. As well as providing standard immunization, essential healthcare equipment and drugs, and campaigns for sensitization against avoidable life-threatening illnesses.

To take a conflict-sensitive approach and to access children in the most inaccessible parts of

South Sudan, UNICEF incorporates rapid response missions (UNICEF South Sudan, 2021b).

Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH)

UNICEF's development intervention plan has been to provide communities with access to safe WASH by providing boreholes, water tankers, and prediction tablets and powders for families.

To construct and maintain latrines and sensitize communities across the country on the value of sanitation and hygiene. To further prevent diseases and ensure a healthier future for the children in South Sudan (UNICEF South Sudan, 2021b).

Climate Change and Flooding

UNICEF in partnership with other foreign aid and development groups supports the flood and climate disaster survivors with essentials such as vaccinations, nutrition supplies, soaps, drugs, and clean water. Minimise the effect of the flood by investing in climate resilience and resistance in South Sudan (UNICEF South Sudan, 2021). And further provide food, clean WASH, and climate resilience. UNICEF claims to take a conflict-sensitive approach in its effort to support South Sudan as a fragile state.

International Rescue Committee (IRC)

In line with the IRC's aid policy *to sustain the rules of war, protect civilians in armed conflict, ensure accountability from violators and ensure aid organizations get better access to vulnerable people*, Crisis Watch (2023) reports that the IRC supported 1.1 million people in South Sudan and 185 of 188 in human development. The IRC takes a conflict-sensitive approach

as it supports South Sudan with lifesaving aid by playing a role in restoring peace and obtaining a better quality of life in conflict and post-conflict.

The IRC has provided emergency support through years of war and a highly vulnerable population in South Sudan. IRC is mostly focused on capacity development in the healthcare sector: upskilling local healthcare personnel, nutrition sensitisation and programme initiatives, and hygiene services. Some of the IRC focus areas are Lakes States, Unity, Northern Bahr el Ghazal and Central Equatoria.

1. To educate government officials and community leaders on the relevance of validating human rights.
2. To provide sanitation, building and reinstating wells and offering nutritional services to stop the further spread of diseases.
3. To develop the capacity of local health workers and help them provide basic and effective health care.
4. To support sexual violence survivors with medical, psychosocial, and legal assistance.
5. To assist SSR returning to the country with emergency training on jobs and livelihoods.

The IRC in collaboration with other foreign aid partners' requests the inclusion of refugees in the national systems and calls for donors to assist with USD 1.33 billion to meet the crucial needs of refugees in South Sudan (Relief Web 2023). In December 2023, the South Sudan Regional Refugee Response Plan was developed by the International Rescue Committee and 108 other aid resource planning partners. The IRC and its partners encourage refugee participation

in climate adaptation strategies, as climate change is a major concern in the country. This fosters self-reliance and protects and strengthens the rights of refugees.

According to Relief Web (2023), the focus of the IRC is its partnership with the national, state, and other local authorities to reinforce effective healthcare, assist IDPs in South Sudan to obtain long-term solutions and provide critical reproductive health and nutrition. As well as promote economic recovery and resilience, and environmental health services to the people of South Sudan.

United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR)

According to the UNHCR (2021) report, the UNHCR in collaboration with the government, aid agencies, and development and peacekeeping actors provide multisectoral support to South Sudan. Based on the UNHCR's aid philosophy *to promote basic human rights, safety, and well-being of refugees*. This comprises life-saving aid, education and capacity development for improved livelihood, and protection of IDPs and refugees that have returned to the region and host communities in the country, through development-focused solutions.

In August 2021, the UNHCR, the UNMISS Head of the Field Office and the UNMISS Protection, Reintegration and Transition team collaborated to discuss effective partnership principles for IDP protection and solutions in South Sudan. Cash and Non-Food Items (NFIs) were provided to over 17,000 IDPs with special needs. A number higher than the initial projected amount because of the need for specialized support and an inflow of new arrivals after the inter-communal conflict. Community-led projects promoting peaceful co-existence were

implemented in offices. This includes police stations, schools, boreholes, accessible and engaging community centres, and life-skill and vocational training and construction of government structures (Global Focus, 2021).

More than 3800 women and girls were provided psychosocial support opportunities and another 17,000 homes were provided GBV awareness on prevention and response. This included conversations with community members, refugees, returnees, and other stakeholders (Global Focus Report, 2021). In applying the age, gender, diversity, and conflict-sensitive approach, participatory assessments were conducted in refugee activity locations such as Urban Juba, Gendrassa, Doro, Gorom Lasu, Ajuong, Pamir, Batil and other areas.

According to the UNHCR 2022 Annual Results Report, an open-door policy and a favourable protection environment for refugees and individuals at risk of statelessness were implemented by the GoSS. Granting all POCs access to South Sudan territories with protection, in line with international standards. The UNHCR in partnership with the government-supported capacity development and strategic partnerships towards this policy implementation. This allowed asylum seekers and people at risk of losing their state to enjoy relative freedom to enjoy medical services, access to other facilities, freedom of movement and self-sustenance. However, access to certain public services was limited. While certain freedom was allowed, there were some arrests where UNHCR and partners helped secure their release and diffused sensitive situations (UNHCR, 2022).

The (UNHCR, 2022) Impact Area Report (IAR) on Realizing Rights in Safe Environments for POC shows that 36 percent of IDPs lived in physically safe and secure settlements with access to facilities. 98 per cent of Refugees and Asylum Seekers resided in physically safe and secure settlements with access to healthy drinking water, access to education, sanitation, and other health facilities. Another 36 per cent of SSRs lived in physically safe and secure settlements with access to facilities.

The IAR on Empowering Communities, Achieving Gender Equality and Other Outcomes for POC (UNHCR, 2021) shows that 66.45 per cent of Refugees and asylum seekers enrolled in primary education. 43.79 per cent of Refugees and asylum seekers enrolled in secondary school. 57.56 per cent of IDPs feel safe walking alone in their neighborhood. 72.55 per cent of IDPs are educated on where to access available GBV services. And another 36.51 per cent find violence against women unacceptable. 34.61 per cent of Refugees and asylum seekers know how to access available GBV services. 35 per cent find abuse against women unacceptable. And 19.78 percent of IDPs, particularly children, participate in community-based child protection programmes. UNHCR and its partners significantly assisted refugees in Agriculture and self-employment opportunities at various levels.

Despite the support to POC, with the long-term civil war one major challenge experienced by the UNHCR and other donors is the availability of weapons within communities in South Sudan-making it convenient for the re-emergence of deadly conflict. It helped that the UNHCR maintained a solid partnership with local, national, international, and community-level stakeholders including about 15 national and international NGOs to ensure the goals were met.

With effective coordination, UNHCR has successfully strengthened its response to impact persons of concern in South Sudan and its fragility (UNHCR, 2021). While taking a conflict-sensitive approach to its collaborations and development activities.

World Bank

As one of the largest development research centres, the World Bank (WB) is continuously supporting the government's attempts to strengthen institutions, and public service delivery and develop resilience and opportunities for quality living in South Sudan (WB, 2023). Due to locust invasion and other climate change situations affecting crops and grazing in South Sudan, the International Development Association of the WB responded with USD 50.7 million in funding to the Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security (MAFS). In 2021 the WB in alliance with the GoSS, the UNOPS and the FOA launched one of its first financed projects for implementation, the ERLP. It aimed to benefit 184,476 households.

According to Acting Country Manager Leslie Mhara (2023), *"The support provided through the ERLP project did a great deal in addressing the immediate to medium-term needs of the vulnerable households. Homes with no able-bodied members in the family to support them. UNOPS is thankful to the GoSS and the World Bank for initiating such critical support to the households and communities affected by the desert locusts."*

Firas Raad, WB Country Manager for South Sudan (2023) said, *"The World Bank projects and collaborations in South Sudan aim to strengthen the government capacity to monitor and respond to future locust attacks. Besides cash assistance and providing public work schemes, the*

World Bank project in South Sudan also aims to open marketplace access for communities, develop the restoration of pastoral and farming systems, and strengthen the government's response and risk capacity." Currently, in addition to efforts on previous social protection projects in South Sudan, the Government and the WB are presently delivering the new USD 129 million SNSOP. This includes access to cash transfers and income-generating opportunities to 96,000 poor and vulnerable homes in 15 selected communities in South Sudan.

As shown in Figure 15 in the WB 2021 Project Data, citizens across the globe including South Sudan, have been beneficiaries of its health, food, capacity-building projects, and development aid.

Figure 9: **WB 2021 Project Data**

Source: **WB Report (2021)**

Based on economic development, the WB is in partnership with the OfD programme and the IMF, focused on development and adherence to best practices and expertise. The Petroleum Governance Initiative (PGI) is a bilateral initiative between the OfD programme and the WB, to provide good petroleum governance under the pillars of sector governance, environmental management, and community development.

Unlike other international aid organizations, the WB is a financial institution. Its ***strategic and financial programs*** support government policies, and economic and institutional reforms to achieve development objectives, beneficial to its ROI. Empirically, while the World Bank is somewhat interested in ending extreme poverty and increasing collective growth, it has no direct interest in South Sudan or other fragile states. As a result, it is not required to consider the context of the crisis in the country or take a conflict-sensitive approach to its financing. Rather, its major concerns are whether the borrower can repay, and that its lending is profitable and would generate a good ROI to allow for continuous support.

African Development Bank (AfDB)

The AfDB institutional strategic policy is ***economic and social progress***, in line with sustainable development goals to drastically reduce poverty. After South Sudan's membership to the AfDB in 2012 and its membership ratification in 2013, it was privy to aid and other development interventions and opportunities. Since then, AfDB aggregate approval to South Sudan has been up to USD 136.79 million (AfDB Group, 2023). In-sector development intervention breakdown comprises a total of **USD 45 million** approved funding towards Agriculture. **USD 38.9 million** sanctioned funds towards the power sector. **USD 45.9 million** cumulative approval towards

multi-sector. A total of **USD 7 million** was approved for funding to the water and sanitation sector.

Currently, there is a USD 108.8 million commitment to seven active operations in the AfDB portfolio for South Sudan. The agriculture sector has the most funding allocation with 41 per cent, the power sector at 35.6%, the multi-sector at 16.5% and the water and sanitation sector at 6.5% (AfDB Group, 2023). With the 2018- 2021 National Development Strategy (NDS), the AfDB in 2019 approved the revised Interim Country Strategy Paper (I-CSP) focused on developing capacity and infrastructure to support the country's goal, to enhance the living conditions and overall quality of life of South Sudanese people. In addition to the revised Interim Country Strategy Paper (I-CSP) in 2021, the AfDB planned to fund finance investment projects and provide technical support with about USD 85.4 million (AfDB Group, 2023).

These include.

The development and access to quality basic education.

The development of strategic urban and rural water supply and sanitation.

The improvement of the East Africa payment system.

Skills and capacity building on business and oil transactions and consultations.

The funding and development of economic resilience.

The advancement of Agriculture infrastructure and value chain inclusion.

The promotion and funds to renewable energy operations.

The development of non-oil national and community-level revenue opportunities.

Furthermore, during the implementation of the updated I-CSP, certain funding and lending strategies were formulated around gender profiling, debt management, youth employment, climate change, and feasibility study for the 400 KV South Sudan-Uganda power interconnection project. This was aimed at informing future project designs and guiding government economic and policy reforms.

In the 2022 AfDB Agriculture Development Intervention in South Sudan, the bank provided a USD 8.1 million grant for food production and its Emergency Food Production Programme (EFPP). The grant included funding for Food Production Markets, Value Addition and Trade Development Project (AMVAT) to reduce food insecurity, and poverty, develop economic growth and community, and family strength for survival and social connection. Due to the impact of the Ukraine war and the increased climate crisis, the EFPP by the AfDB aims to support and prioritize an additional 600,000 highly vulnerable people in South Sudan who recently experienced the most flood crisis which affected their farms and overall household sustenance.

According to Nnenna Nwabufo, AfDB Director General for East Africa, while the AMVAT project is a continuous exercise, the focus is on the food crisis and inadequate supply of essential value chain inputs for agriculture in South Sudan. With a focus on the improvement of the Agricultural Value Chain, production, and productivity in South Sudan. By providing better seeds (about 498 million tons of Sorghum seeds, 10 million tons of rice seeds and 498 million cowpea seeds), fertilizers (30 million tons of fertilizers), and add-on services for farmers, essentially developing institutional capacity within the agriculture sector.

At project completion, the aim is to ensure a sustainable increase in agricultural activities, encourage climate-smart agriculture, improve food security, promote better income, and improve the overall quality of life of the farmers. This is in consideration of existing conflict, as the AfDB is sensitive to the fragility of South Sudan and takes a reasonable level of conflict sensitivity in its support strategy. The AfDB Country Manager for South Sudan, Themba Bhebhe said *“To ensure these measures are effective and sustainable, the project has provided training for thousands of farmers, mostly women, on improved agronomic practices and proper application of fertilizers.”*

More than organization-led aid, scholars argue that country-led foreign aid is more self-serving. Countries donate millions of dollars and have laws that enforce a percentage of their GDP to be given to conflict-affected, fragile, or developing countries, to an end that serves the donor country. According to Duncan (2021), a major aspect of this monetary, material or service assistance by donor countries are in the long-term to ***Secure their Security, Build Economic and Trade Ties, Obtain Diplomatic Support and Build Allies, a Form of Reparation, Tackle Global Issues, For Prestige, or to Promote National Values.***

The country and organization aid philosophies highlight their focus and the extent they take a conflict-sensitive approach to development assistance in South Sudan amid the conflict and post-conflict recovery. Part of this is ensuring the local leaders are involved and are impartial. As countries and organizations provide aid and consider a conflict-sensitive approach to development interventions, their implementations are mostly theme-based, executed through agencies, on specialized areas and perceived levels of impact.

The next chapter discusses foreign aid and development intervention themes and allocations to South Sudan.

Chapter 4

Introduction

This chapter discusses foreign aid and development intervention theme programmes in South Sudan in the conflict and post-conflict era. Some key programmes include the Women, Peace, and Security (WPS), Education, Food and Clean Water, Climate Resilience and Health Care.

Foreign aid-themed development support could reflect the donors' strength or their level of conflict sensitivity to the condition of the beneficiary state. It examines the extent these programmes take a conflict-sensitive approach to development intervention.

Women Peace and Security (WPS)

The WPS is assumed keen on conflict-sensitivity development as conflict plays a major role in the attacks and prejudice against women. The Gender, Peace, and Security (GPS) unit established as a stand-alone in 2016 was aimed to oversee the implementation of the WPS agenda to prevent prejudice and violence against women and girls in conflict (Fox, 2021). This involves actively promoting women's participation and inclusion in peacemaking and peacebuilding efforts, electoral and political processes, actively prioritising peace by preventing and addressing conflict-related sexual violence and programmatic advertising by promoting mainstreaming in all projects through resource allocations, gender markers and tracking.

The WPS agenda is happening at a critical time when the GoSS under the Ministry of Gender, Child and Social Welfare and the UN Women's Support embarks on developing its 2nd National Action Plan on the UN Security Council Resolution 1325 on 2023-2027 WPS (UN Women Africa,

2022). The National Action Plan focuses on four pillars in the state, Prevention, Participation, Protection, Relief, and Recovery which represent efforts towards growth in South Sudan.

Balosoro (2022) said, *“If there is no peace, women suffer the most”*. He organised with the support of the UN Women, a consultation and gathering of government representatives, security sector officials, civil society actors and national-level development partner representatives in a dialogue. This was focused on the South Sudan National Action Plan (SSNAP) plans to protect women and girls in South Sudan. Particularly in the armed conflict-affected environment, to protect and promote human rights, end violence and importantly, ensure equal participation of women in peace discussions and national reconstruction plans.

Due to the progress of the implementation of the first SSNAP and the significant accomplishment of women’s inclusion in the observation and negotiations in the peace discussions, the Revitalized Peace Agreement on the Resolution of the Conflict in South Sudan (R-ARCSS) was signed in 2018. In 2015 women made up 15 percent of delegates leading peace discussions and in 2018 women made up 25 percent of the Coalition and Official Delegates. This later increased to a 35 per cent involvement, with seven of 17 civil society signatories representing conflict parties in the 2018 peace agreement as women (National Action Plan, 2021).

Mohammed (2022), the UN Women Acting Deputy Country Representative in South Sudan commented that in addition to the percentage increase in women's involvement in peace discussions, country reconstruction and other official delegations in South Sudan, for the first

time, the women gained signatory status on the peace agreement and the implementation mechanisms. She emphasized that the new SSNAP aims to address insights and carry over strategic goals from the first successfully implemented SSNAP.

The WPS in South Sudan adopted by the UN Security Council emphasizes commitment to **End GBV, Achieve Gender Equality and Empower all Women and Girls**. The International Organization for Migration (IOM), in 2021 provided support to the women and girls in South Sudan to end GBV. 55 females and 51 males were trained on effective responses to GBV. This includes responding to disclosures and providing referrals, and support to survivors.

Skills development, psychosocial and capacity-building opportunities were provided for 370 women and girls in 20 different groups across Juba, Tonj South and Jur River area. 105 girls, 101 boys, 101 young women, 130 young men, 100 older women and 95 older men were engaged in multigenerational discussions to sensitize and promote productive masculinity and end GBV. 11 radio shows aired on ending GBV awareness- 4,955 South Sudanese people were reached and sensitized through the radio outreach. Capacity building on GBV through training on gender discussion facilitation and active community awareness and engagement in schools, social clubs, worship centres and other aspects. 75 community structures developed between Juba and Wau.

Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH)

Safe WASH has contributed to healthier living, improved students' presence in schools and established healthier and more resilient communities. Part of the USAID WASH activity includes the provision of safe water to IDPs in Malakal- one of the largest cities in South Sudan amongst

other regions. Other organizations supporting the WASH agenda in South Sudan include the ECHO and the FCDO.

In 2021 a water yard was constructed by the International Organisation for Migration (IOM), funded by USAID in Wau Lokoloko in South Sudan (IOM, 2021). Being the largest WASH service provider in the PoC and IDP sites in South Sudan, the IOM ensured that 153,596 IDPs got safe WASH services daily with liquid and solid waste management (Relief International, 2023).

According to the IOM South Sudan 2021 WASH Programme implementation, **2,222,423** people were impacted by Safe WASH services with the following highlights:

1. **666** hand-washing devices and facilities were built and conserved. Alongside 3 Points of Entry sites with more WASH services.
2. **57** new boreholes were built, **118** were renovated and 9 Solar water yards were built.
3. A total of **9,908** beneficiaries of the IOM's Community-Based Total Sanitation Programme. This included a development in the role and decision-making capacity of **414** women in leadership training.
4. The construction of latrines to withstand extreme weather conditions for homes, schools, and clinics.
5. Emergency clean water tanks were provided to crisis-affected areas.
6. **31,023** WASH kits including body and laundry soap and sanitary towels. And other **10,179** Dignity Kits provided across South Sudan.
7. **1,007** WASH volunteers were trained on GBV Mainstreaming.

Food Security and Hunger Eradication

Food insecurity could lead to deaths among children and adults (Sumsion et al., 2023). To minimise food insecurity and maximise agricultural improvement, and food development and availability in South Sudan, in 2019 the United States launched a landmines and Explosives Remnants of War (ERW) eradication. A means to encourage the return of IDPs (US Department of State, 2023).

According to the 2022 WFP report, 5.6 million South Sudanese people were supported and impacted by the WFP. The WFP aid philosophy is ***to establish and support increased food security and eradicate global hunger***. According to the WFP South Sudan Situation Report (2023), the Food Agriculture Organization (FAO) in its 2022 Crop and Food Security Assessment Mission reported an estimated 11.5 per cent increase in food security from 2021. The statement highlights that this improvement was due to the return of IDPs to South Sudan and their engagement in Agriculture. Until the unfortunate recent flooding, hike in fuel prices and food insecurity due to the depreciation of the South Sudanese Pound (WFP, 2023).

In 2023, the WFP provided 14,901 metric tons of food and USD 4.5 million cash distribution to 1.9 million South Sudanese people- including refugees and IDPs. The WFP further provided emergency food to 23,265 new IDPs across South Sudan but were affected by funding limitations that led to a USD 466 million funding gap sometime in 2023. This reduced their target beneficiary number from 7.7 million to 5.4 million, causing a percentage reduction in the number of targeted beneficiaries from 65 per cent to 53 per cent, to 33 per cent and 18 per cent, respectively.

With reports of deaths due to hunger in Payam the WFP and UNICEF in partnership with other aid organizations provide food and nutrition services in the lowest administrative counties in South Sudan. And continue to help with case identification and food and nutrition services via static and mobile sites. Furthermore, in the context of the conflict, the WFP takes a conflict-sensitive approach by prioritising and providing 70 per cent of the food and portions allocated to people within counties that are faced with halved portions and increased food insecurity due to corruption or poor administration.

The WFP intends to scale up resilience in the CSP of 2023- 2025 with a focus on expanding, restoring, and maintaining important infrastructure such as the riverways, ports, bridges, and roads to reduce dependence on expensive air transportation in South Sudan. This would enable the operational effectiveness of humanitarian teams, develop trade activities, and improve access to markets and other services.

Quality Education

According to the UNICEF and UNESCO Joint Statement on Education in 2021, 18 per cent of schools were dysfunctional. Some due to the impacts of conflict and climate disasters and others due to untrained and unqualified teachers (UNICEF, South Sudan, 2023). However, in recent times there has been a significant improvement in education in South Sudan, with the enrollment of more children in school. In the last decade, there has been a 20 per cent increase in the number of South Sudanese children in schools and more girls are interested, enrolled, and most importantly stay in school. The 2030 Sustainable Development Agenda 4 to invest in and make education a priority is also a priority for UNICEF in South Sudan. Also, there has been

a call to the GoSS, partners and donors to prioritise and actively support education, to increase budget allocation to the education sector and to finance and increase accountability of the education sector (Moller, 2023) and (UNICEF, South Sudan, 2023). This includes a call to take the required steps to implement strategies that provide and protect a better future for the younger generation. And maximise potential local and global growth opportunities through an effective education system.

According to Banda (2023), *“Education limits conflict and promotes peace.”* By investing in the education of children, youth and women, South Sudan could develop a more peaceful and sustainable environment. At the 2022 UN Transforming Education Summit (TES) the GoSS promised its dedication to rebuilding education and initiating accelerated inclusive and quality education opportunities for the people of South Sudan- prioritising the marginalized people.

Health Care and Well-Being

In 2016, the South Sudan Ministry of Health established the 2016-2026 National Health Policy (NHP) focusing on developing a vision and strategic direction for the health sector, to be executed in two five-year strategic plans: 2021-2021 and 2021-2026. The objective is ***to improve the national health system and partnerships that manage the risks and limitations to the effective delivery of the Basic Package of Health and Nutrition Services (BPHNS)***. Including the efficient response to quality and safety concerns within communities.

The Support to Health Services in South Sudan Project: Strengthening Resilience of Communities was established in 2019 to contribute to the development of better health and well-being of the people of South Sudan. Its specific focus was to increase sufficient access to

standard health care, including balance and nutrition services to pregnant women and children (Emergency Trust Fund for Africa, 2019). To ensure progress and success in health care and well-being, South Sudan is collaborating with international aid agencies such as CARE. This is to strengthen healthcare frameworks through mobility, monitoring and effective response, sensitization, empowering and educating South Sudan women leaders, and community health workers and increase the WASH team and support.

For this, the South Sudan healthcare sector receives part USD 2 million in aid from CARE. Additionally, CARE coordinated with the Sudanese Ministry for Education and Health to sensitise and expand medical training in communities and wade off the lack of information (Thelwell, 2021). Furthermore, the U.S. announced a USD 108 million assistance to South Sudan to develop more state-of-the-art health frameworks and systems.

The core of foreign aid and development intervention towards health care in South Sudan is to develop better health and well-being for the people post-conflict and as they recover from the crisis. And to ensure a foundation for a more efficient and effective health system, through funding and collaborations with the GoSS and other development organisations with shared values (Anib et al., 2022).

Chapter 5

Introduction

This chapter examines some of the challenges experienced by the foreign aid actors and development intervention activities mentioned in chapters 3 and 4. It also presents learnings and observations from this study and its contribution to the overall conflict sensitivity approach to development interventions in South Sudan as a fragile state.

Foreign Aid and Development Intervention Challenges in South Sudan

Some of the main challenges faced by foreign aid and donors in South Sudan include the persistent violent conflict and state fragility, climate crisis, poor resilience and other human factors.

Human factors more than other challenges stand at the core of manipulating foreign assistance in South Sudan. This includes issues such as poor public management systems and corruption. The UNMISS 2022 report on violence against civilians in South Sudan indicated that violence against civilians had increased by 2 per cent compared to 2021. With levels of documented violent incidents rising by 27 per cent, from 714 acts of violence in 2021 to 982 in 2022. The first three weeks of March saw increased attacks on humanitarian workers, assets and looting of humanitarian food and other supplies from convoys, limiting WFP and other humanitarian partners' capacity to reach vulnerable people in some parts of the country.

The United States calls upon the Revitalized Transitional Government of National Unity to take urgent action to address these issues.

Learnings and Observations

Some findings are that foreign aid country-led actors such as the US government, Britain, Norway and Japan, and organisation-led development activities as identified in chapters 3 and 4 work with certain philosophies and approaches. Each plays into the interests and objectives of the country or the organization, and their level of priority. To put things in perspective, billions of Dollars are channelled to developing countries like South Sudan year in and year out still aid seems ineffective. According to Sraieb (2016), international aid ineffectiveness can be attributed to donor motivation and factors that drive foreign assistance, such as economic policy and power, continuous colonial (soft) power, neoclassic and strategic realism. In the overall framework, the approach adopted influences donors' interest levels and decisions to consider or adopt a conflict-sensitive approach to aid provided in South Sudan.

In considering the extent foreign aid in South Sudan takes a conflict-sensitive approach to development intervention and its criticality, it seems that conflict sensitivity has been reasonably examined and adopted at various times, such as through support to the IGAD-led peace process by the Trioka, the 2015 peace accord and the UNs support for the implementation of the renewed peace agreement and transitional Government of National Unity in 2018 (Chapter 3.), still the country remains in a state of fragility. Thus, South Sudan needs to be willing to rise from the ashes. As foreign aid actors understand and adopt a more conflict-sensitive approach to support provided in South Sudan, the human factor plays a critical role in ending the conflict and accepting aid and development.

Like many other developing countries with natural resources, South Sudan may also be affected by the “curse of natural resources”. The distribution of its oil, which makes up 98% of its export revenue, has been a major source of conflict between the ethnic groups at war and the struggle for power, alongside the country's defective political and judicial system. The country's desire for fairness and equal distribution of resources, power and benefits between private and public sectors and its ability to better allocate public finances and budgets for the overall improvement and development of every citizen is a great place to start. The key concept is that it begins with the people of South Sudan.

Ultimately, the different groups in South Sudan should embrace a willingness for peace and development. As well as conforming to peace dialogues and agreements and moving past ethnic conflicts, human rights violations, corruption, inter-ethnic violence, sexual abuse, and dysfunctional judicial system. Only then can foreign aid begin to make sense, and there be effective conversations to tackle real national issues with further hope of benefiting from solutions presented through international aid. Issues such as climate change, industry, innovation and infrastructure, economic growth and decent work, reduced inequality, food production and consumption, quality education, good health, clean water, and sanitation, zero hunger, no poverty and ending the internal displacement of the people of South Sudan.

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Appendices

Table 1	Milestones of the UN's work in South Sudan	48
Figure 1	Horizontal Inequality Framework	16
Figure 2	South Sudan in Focus	20
Figure 3	South Sudan Ethnic Composition	21
Figure 4	South Sudan GDP Per Capita 2008- 2023	29
Figure 5	Real GDP Index 2011- 2021	32
Figure 6	Estimated South Sudan Oil Revenue	35
Figure 7	Norwegian Official Development Aid, 2015	39
Figure 8	Japan Exports to South Sudan	43
Figure 9	World Bank 2021 Project Data	57